

MANUFACTURING AND TESTING OF CURVED FIBER COMPOSITES USING VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING (VARTM)

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ABSTRACT

The resin infusion (aka. Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding VARTM) process has significant potential to be used to manufacture curved composites. Another way to produce curved or complex geometry is to use 3D printers. 3D or FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling) printers are now being used to produce relatively cheaper curved parts using thermoplastics such as PLA. However, the strength and mechanical performance of these parts is limited and can be enhanced if the polymer is reinforced with a type of fiber for instance. Research is being carried out to produce fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites but that process is expected to be more expensive than the alternative methods such as injection or compression molding. In this research molds will be created using an FDM printer to manufacture curved composites via the resin injection process, i.e. with epoxy resin system and glass/carbon/flax fiber reinforcement. By replacing the costly metallic molds by significantly cheaper PLA molds, the cost of production will further be reduced. Hence, using double-sided PLA molds will not be a threat to the overall cost of the composite part in question compared to double-sided matched molds used in compression molding. Shear strength of the manufactured composite parts will be found. The results showed that this method is effective for a cheaper production of curved epoxy resin composites. However, the strength of the part will decrease as the curved profile gets more complicated unless the basic resin infusion process is altered.

1 INTRODUCTION

The resin infusion (aka. Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding VARTM) process has been developed over the last twenty years to manufacture large-scale composite parts for commercial and military applications. This technique is being increasingly used to produce parts and tools in the marine, wind energy, automotive and aerospace sectors, being particularly suitable for medium to large components, and low production runs. Significant amount of research is being carried out to manufacture complex shaped composites using resin infusion and test the composite parts both destructively and non-destructively.

Fused deposition modelling (FDM) is a special Layered Manufacturing (LM) technique in which each section is fabricated through vector style deposition of building blocks, called roads, which are then stacked layer by layer to fabricate the final object. The 3D printer used in this research uses the same concept. Anna Bellini [1] laid emphasis on improving the liquefier dynamics of FDM because

this technology is believed to bring about the possibility of fabricating not only a model but even the finished product or a mold for use in further manufacturing.

LeBlanc and Shukla [2] studied the response of E-Glass/Vinyl ester curved composite panels subjected to underwater explosive loading. They laid importance of non-destructive testing and showed that photography and computational tools can serve to support experimental test results and show promise for use as an alternative to testing to support structural designs utilizing composite materials. Teoh and Hsiao [3] indicated that the spring-in angle of a curved specimen decreases as the number of curing stages increases. The spring-in effect is the reduction of a consolidated curved composite part when it is released from the mold. Their research can be used to improve the dimensional instability problem for manufacturing of curved composites. Besides this, they also stated that the curing process of a thick composite also faces the thermal management challenge due to the high exothermic reaction rate and low thermal conductivity of resin. Ho and co-workers [4] stated that poor wettability, poor bonding and degradation at the fiber/matrix interface (a hydrophilic and hydrophobic effect) and damage of the fiber during the manufacturing process are the main causes of the reduction of the composites' strength. Kuo [5] devised an economical method to fabricate epoxy-based composite mold inserts using rapid prototyping and rapid tooling technique. Kuo laid importance of producing cheap molds for different manufacturing processes. Oterkus and co-workers [6] worked on a non-destructive method to test the structural integrity of curved composites. The method was based on finite element method and the peridynamics theory. Minakuchi and co-workers [7] also developed a non-destructive life cycle monitoring system and an advanced quality assurance method for curved composite parts to improve the design and manufacturing of the composites.

In this research a FDM printer will be used to create molds to manufacture curved composites via the resin injection process, i.e. VARTM with epoxy resin system and glass/carbon fiber reinforcement. Both negative and positive molds will be produced to "muffle" the reinforcement material. Composites will be manufactured using single-sided and double-sided molds. It is expected to achieve a better surface finish with the double-sided mold upgrading the idea of Professor Summerscales [8], who suggested to use a flexible vacuum bag instead of a double-sided mold. He was referring to the costly metallic molds but in this case we are talking about significantly cheaper PLA molds. Hence, using double-sided PLA molds will not be a threat to the overall cost of the composite part in question. The results will be used for comparison and to show the acceptability of the manufactured composites.

3 MATERIALS

Carbon fiber (93 g/m²), glass fiber (300 g/m²) and coarse twill flax fiber (550 g/m²) were used as reinforcements. All fiber reinforcements were twill type. Figure 1 shows the three fiber reinforcements.

Figure 1: (a) Glass fiber, (b) Carbon fiber and (c) Flax fiber

Larit epoxy resin system was used where the ratio of the resin (L-160) and hardener (502) was

100:40 by mass. Gelling time was approximately 50 minutes after careful mixing and degassing for 15 minutes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 3-D mold printing

In order to print the infusion molds, the “Mendelmax FM Pro” in version 1.5 has been used. The printer built in a modular way is a cost-effective option in comparison to an industrial FDM printer. In Table 1 the printer settings are displayed. A nozzle diameter of 0.35 mm was used to gain a reasonable printing quality. With a nozzle temperature of 200 °C, the PLA has shown proper melt behavior and printing accuracy. Due to the staircase effect, the molds have been printed in perpendicular direction to the front side. As a result, the front side itself shows the best surface quality, the printer is able to produce. A solid infill ratio of 35 % has been found suitable to withstand the applied pressure during resin infusion and preserves the mold from collapsing under pressure due to applied vacuum. If printing time is not the primary issue, a higher degree of filling provides more resistance to the outer pressure.

Table 1: FDM printer parameter

Nozzle diameter	0.35 mm
Filament diameter	1.75 mm
Nozzle temperature	205 °C first layer, 200 °C remaining layers
Bed temperature	60 °C first layer, 55 °C remaining layers
Layer height	0.15 mm
Feed rate	38 mm/s
Infill solidity ratio	35 %
Max. part size (Length x Width x Height)	150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm

2.2 VARTM Setup

Figure 2 shows the schematic of experimental setup employed for the resin infusion (VARTM) process. The fiber reinforcement was kept inside the single sided or double sided mold. The mold was covered with a nylon bag so that it can be reused and the manufactured composite part can be separated from the mold after manufacturing.

Figure 2: Experimental setup schematic (VARTM)

A finely perforated fabric industrially known as peel ply fabric was used to pull vacuum from the mold. The vent catch pot was used so that if any excess resin is drawn out of the mold, it can stay in the catch-pot rather than damaging the vacuum pump. Moreover, near the vent, a breathing material was stuffed to decrease the filling speed of the resin and to block the resin from going to the vent catch-pot or the pump.

2.2 Plan of manufacturing experiments

The plan was to evaluate the performance of a FDM printer by using molds to manufacture carbon and glass fiber reinforced composites and to check on their structural integrity by using tensile and non-destructive testing. Table 2 presents the manufacturing plan. Manufacturing will be started from simpler curvatures and proceed to more complicated structures depending on the ability of the 3D printer. Three reinforcing materials are used for a good comparison. All experiments will be repeated for cross checking the results. Number of layers of the fibers will be infused with resin will be varied to keep the mass of the fiber reinforcements constant. All the manufacturing details will be kept constant for repeatable results. Shear tests will be carried out to show the structural integrity of the manufactured composite parts and thickness of the parts will be measured to determine the dimensional stability of the composite parts.

Table 2: Experimental Plan

#	Curvature	Material
1	Singly curved less complicated (single curve) (SC_1)	Carbon fiber
2		Glass fiber
3		Flax fiber
4	Singly curved more complicated (two curves) (SC_2)	Carbon fiber
5		Glass fiber
6		Flax fiber
7	Hemisphere (DC)	Carbon fiber
8		Glass fiber
9		Flax fiber

2.3 Shear testing

Short beam shear tests were conducted on samples to evaluate the effect of variation in the kind of fiber and mold curvature on the mechanical strength of the composites. Samples taken from parts manufactured according to the manufacturing plan were tested for short beam shear strength under ASTM D-2344 standards. A total of ten specimens were cut out of each composite part to be used for testing. Since the thickness of the composite parts was expected to be around 4 mm, the specimen length was six times and the specimen width was twice the thickness. The specimens were cut out from the manufactured composite parts. Figure 3 shows the testing apparatus setup on the INSTRON

5567 machine to perform the three point bending test. The crosshead speed was set to 1 mm/minute to prevent abrupt failures. The criteria for specimen failure were 30% load drop or a flexure extension of 10 mm. The span length was 16 mm for all the rectangular specimens.

Figure 3: Short beam shear testing setup

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The composites parts manufactured via the resin infusion process were tested for the shear strengths. Thickness at six points on all the parts was measured and the average thickness was determined for each type of part. This section will outline the significant results that led to a few comparisons.

4.1 Curvature

The curve geometry of the finished parts was very much what was expected given the geometry of the mold. The double curved geometry, which is actually a hemispherical shape in this research, was not absolutely achieved due to wrinkling of the reinforcing layers. This wrinkling can be reduced by tailored cuts of the reinforcement to adjust with the hemispherical shape. However, this procedure would cause a major reduction in mechanical strength in the treated area.

Figure 4 shows the average thickness taken at six positions on the three curvatures. The first one is a simple single curve (SC_1). The second one is two single curves in one profile (SC_2). The third one is doubly curved or a hemispherical shape (DC). The average thickness of the part increases by 0.5 mm from SC_1 to SC_2 and then SC_2 to DC with the same experimental conditions. This implies that the achieved fiber volume fraction for a part with a more complicated curve will be less compared to the one with a less complicated curve. As the curve gets more complicated, it is more difficult for vacuum to drape the reinforcement on the mold and hence more resin flows and impregnates the fiber reinforcement. This effect can be reduced by pulling vacuum from vent and inlet in the post filling stage rather than just clamping the inlet. It will be interesting to see how close the thickness values can be brought for the given three curvatures under these conditions. On the other hand, by pulling full vacuum from both the inlet and the vent in the post-filling stage, voids will be induced to the composite part, which can considerably reduce the mechanical strength of the part. Hence it is a trade-off between the dimensional accuracy and the mechanical strength of the part.

Figure 4: Average thickness of the singly and doubly curved composites

4.2 Type of reinforcement

The three reinforcements used possessed different areal densities and are the commonly used types of fiber reinforcements in the industry. All three reinforcements were chosen to be twill types so that there is less effect of the fiber architecture on the quality of the manufactured part. Figure 5 shows the shear strengths of composite parts produced using flax, carbon fiber and glass fiber. The results were quite close and within 0.2 mm difference for all the SC_1 parts. This is indicating that most of the shear strength of the composite part is based on the epoxy resin used because not much difference in the shear strength values can be seen for the three different fiber types. If a comparison is made between the different curvatures, then it is seen that there is not much difference between SC_1 and SC_2 but there is a marked difference in the shear strengths of single and double curved composite part. This low shear strength is mainly because of the complicated curvature itself and partly because of the indirect effect of this double curve on the manufacturing process. When the part geometry gets more complicated the compaction of the fiber reinforcement due to vacuum is weaker as mentioned earlier. The overall shear strength values of the curved composites are less than those of curved parts produced using resin transfer molding. However, the cost of manufacturing parts using this method is significantly lower than resin transfer molding.

Figure 5: Shear strengths of the composites

4.3 Comparison of single and double sided mold

This research also aimed to compare the manufacturing of the composites using single sided PLA molds with the double sided counterparts. There was not much difference between the shear strength values of parts manufactured using the two arrangements. Since the compaction pressure is not more than the atmospheric pressure, there is not much residual stress due to the double sided molds. This led to a lesser difference in the shear strength values of the parts manufactured by the two arrangements. Under high compaction pressures, double sided molds tend to induce high residual stresses in the parts. In this case the molds are made of PLA and not steel to they cannot withstand a high compaction pressure anyway. However, there was a slightly more variation of thickness over the surface of parts produced by single sided molds compared to those produced by double sided mold. Figure 6 shows the thickness variation over the surface of parts produced using single and double sided molds. The parts produced with single sided molds have a larger scatter of thickness values than the ones produced with the double sided arrangement. To produce parts with a more stable thickness over the surface, double sided molds looked promising and maintained a good consistency of thickness over the surface of the manufactured parts.

Figure 6: Thickness variation of parts manufactured using single and double sided molds

4.4 Dimensional accuracy and shape

The challenge in this research was to achieve the targeted shapes. The PLA molds used were considered significantly weaker than any other molds being used in the industry to produce epoxy resin composites. However, since the compaction pressure was not more than the atmospheric pressure, the weak PLA molds were able to withstand this stress and convert that to shape the composite part. Figure 7 shows a simple single curved carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite part. The shape and dimensions are quite in line with what was targeted. Especially for the simple singly curved parts, the shape and dimensions were very consistent for all fiber reinforcements.

Figure 7: Simple singly curved composite (SC_1)

Figure 8 shows the more complicated singly curved carbon fiber composite. The shape and dimensions for this type of part were also quite in line with the targeted ones. Both the parts in figure 7 and 8 are manufactured using a double sided mold so that is also a reason why the shape dimensions are quite consistent. Although, parts manufactured by the single sided molds were considerably consistent in the shape and dimensional accuracy.

Figure 8: Complicated singly curved composite (SC_2)

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes a method to manufacture curved composites using resin infusion (VARTM) and cheap PLA molds created by 3D printing (FDM). Three fiber reinforcements were used to successfully manufacture three types of curved composite profiles using single and double sided PLA molds. Shear strengths and thickness of each part was measured and the results were used to draw a few comparisons between the fiber types, mold types and the curvature profiles. The results showed that using double sided molds induces a better consistency in shape and dimensional accuracy of the composites compared to single sided molds. Shear strength and fiber volume fraction decreases significantly from single to double curved composite parts. A higher fiber volume fraction can be achieved by modifying the basic resin infusion process (clamped inlet) but then again it will be a trade-off between the composite strength and the dimensional stability. It was found that the compaction pressure used in this research, which is equivalent to atmospheric pressure, supports the manufacture of the composites using the relatively weak PLA molds. Carbon fiber, glass fiber and flax, which are mostly used as reinforcements in the industry, were all supporting this method to produce curved epoxy resin composites. This method will reduce the overall cost of manufacturing curved composites compared to processes using rigid molds. Furthermore, the stiffness of the mold produced by 3D-printing can be increased by using polymers with a higher modulus and heat distortion temperature.

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